

Assessment of the contribution of different roof types to achieving sustainable development

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Abstract The sustainability of cities is being influenced by their roofs, which cover an increasingly high proportion of built-up areas and whose design is crucial to control their potential economic, environmental and social impacts in a context of urban sprawl and Climate Change. For this reason, this research aimed at developing a Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) methodology combining the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) to support the selection of four representative roof types (self-protected, gravel, floating and green roofs) according to their contribution to sustainability, based on their performance across a list of indicators aligned to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The analysis was carried out under three different climate scenarios (Mediterranean, Oceanic and Continental) and relied on the judgments provided by a panel of experts in the building sector to both refine and weight the proposed indicators. The results proved that green roofs were the most sustainable alternative for all the climate scenarios evaluated, by virtue of their insulation, recycling, cost, energy, water and ecosystem-related benefits. Consequently, this type of roof emerges as a multifunctional solution to be strongly considered in the design of planning strategies seeking urban regeneration.

Keywords Climate scenarios; Expert judgment; Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis; Roofs; Sustainability

1. Introduction

Roofs occupy about 20-25% of urban surfaces [1], whilst the buildings they cover account for 40% of total energy consumption worldwide and 36% of European greenhouse gas emissions [2]. As such, roofs are key drivers for ensuring sustainable economic development, environmental protection and social welfare, especially in a context of

40 urban sprawl and Climate Change whereby more than half the world's population live in
41 cities [3] whose resilience is being exceeded by the intensity of weather events [4].

42 On the one hand, urbanisation favours the presence of impervious surfaces and
43 reduces evapotranspiration, which in turns exacerbates the Urban Heat Island effect and,
44 consequently, the warming of cities [5]. The presence of impervious areas also has
45 relevant impacts on water quality and quantity [6], whilst the car-dependent lifestyle
46 derived from urban population growth leads to a rise in air pollution [7]. On the other
47 hand, global temperature is forecasted to rise for decades to come, particularly in urban
48 areas as a result of anthropogenic development [8]. There is also evidence of an increase
49 in extreme rainfall intensity in recent years, boosting the magnitude and frequency of
50 flash floods [9].

51 The design of roofs impacts on these phenomena, influencing the resilience of cities
52 to both of them in terms of alterations in temperature, water-related processes, energy and
53 air quality [10]. Furthermore, roofs can also contribute to economic growth,
54 environmental safeguard and human wellbeing [11]. Therefore, the planning of these
55 elements provides a multifaceted opportunity to help meeting some of the 17 Sustainable
56 Development Goals (SDGs) established by the United Nations in 2015 [12], which seek
57 to protect the planet and ensure prosperity for all.

58 In line with these considerations, several investigations have been conducted over the
59 past two decades to support the selection of roof types based on their performance across
60 multiple criteria. An overview of the most relevant studies for the target of this research
61 is provided below. Nassar et al. (2003) [13] developed a computer tool to select suitable
62 combinations of building assemblies, including the evaluation of asphalt, plastic and
63 metallic roofs in terms of durability, insulation, permeability, maintenance, warranty,
64 compatibility and serviceability. Abeysundara et al. (2009) [14] presented a life cycle-
65 based matrix to support the choice of sustainable materials for two types of roofs (asbestos
66 sheet and clay tile) according to their price and affordability, embodied energy,
67 environmental impacts, comfort, aesthetics, strength, durability and constructability.
68 Collier et al. (2013) [15] evaluated the sustainability of three roofing technologies
69 (reflective, vegetated and solar roofs) across the triple bottom line, considering their costs,
70 resource usage, environmental impacts and welfare benefits. Gagliano et al. (2015) [16]
71 undertook a comparative study of the energy savings and environmental advantages
72 provided by three alternatives (conventional, cool and green roof), based on dynamic
73 simulations of the energy balance of a building under temperate climate conditions.
74 Canto-Perello et al. (2015) [17] assessed three roofs formed of prefabricated concrete,
75 steel and laminated wood structures under economic (costs), environmental (emissions
76 and energy) and social (fireproofing, use of local materials and aesthetics) criteria.
77 Loikkanen et al. (2017) [18] evaluated different energy solutions for a glass roof using
78 their internal rate of return, energy efficiency, CO₂ emissions, and attractiveness as
79 decision criteria. Apart from ad-hoc roof analyses, several studies have appraised green

80 roofs in comparison with other green infrastructure systems, such as bioretention cells,
81 infiltration trenches or permeable pavements [19–21].

82 The revision of previous research revealed a knowledge gap in the design of methods
83 or tools to support the selection of roofs according to the principles of sustainable
84 development, using indicators that contribute to measuring the achievement of the SDGs.
85 The representativeness of the roof types addressed and the evaluation of different climate
86 scenarios were other aspects having room for improvement. Hence, this research emerged
87 to meet these requirements by assessing the sustainability of representative roof types
88 across a refined list of sustainability indicators under three different climate scenarios.

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90 2. Methodology

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92 The main steps of the methodology proposed to address the evaluation of the contribution
93 of roofs to sustainability are outlined in Figure 1. From a conceptual point of view, the
94 approach taken consisted of establishing a series of energetic, hydrologic, environmental,
95 social, economic and structural indicators with which to assess the sustainability of
96 several roof types under different climate scenarios. From a technical perspective, this
97 was accomplished using Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) methods, which
98 enabled appraising the performance of the roofs across a refined list of weighted
99 indicators.

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Figure 1. Outline of the methodology designed to assess the contribution of different roof types to sustainable development

105 2.1. Definition of the initial list of sustainability indicators

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107 An indicator can be defined as a measure providing guidance about how to value a certain
 108 parameter. In this case, the use of indicators was framed within a MCDA model aimed at
 109 assessing the contribution of different types of roofs to sustainability under different
 110 climate scenarios. To this end, an initial set of indicators as listed in Table 1 was proposed
 111 according to the principles included in the United Nations Sustainable Development
 112 Goals (SDGs).

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Table 1. Initial list of indicators proposed to assess the sustainability of roofs

I_j	Indicator	Units
I_1	Albedo coefficient	Dimensionless
I_2	Solar power	%
I_3	Carbon sequestration	g C/m ²
I_4	Embedded carbon	kg CO ₂ eq./m ²
I_5	Embedded energy	MJ/m ₂
I_6	Runoff attenuation	%
I_7	Water purification	Score
I_8	Reduction of runoff temperature	°C
I_9	Biodiversity	Yes/No
I_{10}	Agricultural productivity	Yes/No
I_{11}	Recycled materials	%
I_{12}	Thermal insulation	cm
I_{13}	Noise control	t/m ³
I_{14}	Life cycle cost	€/m ²
I_{15}	Aesthetics	Score
I_{16}	Dead load	kN/m ²
I_{17}	Roof protection	±°C

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116 The Albedo coefficient (I_1) represents the portion of solar radiation reflected to the
 117 atmosphere. Hence, the greater the Albedo of a roof, the less it is heated by insolation.
 118 Consequently, this indicator is related to the impacts of roofs on the Urban Heat Island
 119 (UHI) effect and the warming of buildings, which might help improving the resilience
 120 against climate hazards considered in SDGs 1 and 13.

121 The second indicator in Table 1 (I_2) concerned the thermoregulatory potential of roofs
 122 and their capacity of attenuating local temperature. This factor might have a positive
 123 effect on the production of solar energy, since high temperatures cause a reduction in the
 124 performance of photovoltaic cells. Therefore, the indicator of solar power can contribute
 125 to meeting the targets of energetic efficiency contemplated in SDG 7.

126 The materials forming the layers of a roof might contribute to capturing atmospheric
 127 carbon, such that roofs act as a natural carbon sink (I_3). This aspect is in line with some
 128 of the targets included in SDGs 3, 11 and 12, which focus on reducing the presence of

129 atmospheric hazards to protect human health, as well as controlling environmental
130 contamination in cities.

131 The next two indicators (I_4 and I_5) consisted of the embedded carbon and energy
132 associated with a roof, from the extraction of raw materials to the construction of the
133 structure. Hence, these indicators, as well as that concerning the use of recycled materials
134 (I_{11}), are related to SDGs 3, 7, 8, 11 and 12, which deal with the effects that resource
135 efficiency may have on humans and cities in terms of energy and environment.

136 Rainfall was added to the list of indicators through the benefits that roofs might
137 provide in terms of reduction of runoff amount (I_6), pollution (I_7) and temperature (I_8).
138 These aspects can be translated into flood mitigation, rainfall purification and protection
139 of flora and fauna against high runoff temperatures, which are concepts extremely linked
140 to the water-related issues highlighted in SDGs 1, 3, 6, 11, 13, 14 and 15.

141 Biodiversity (I_9) and agricultural productivity (I_{10}) referred to the potential of roofs
142 for supporting the presence of animal and plant species and the growth of crops,
143 respectively. These indicators, which strongly depend on the characteristics of the surface
144 layer of the roofs, may aid to meet several targets seeking the achievement of sustainable
145 food, communities and life in SDGs 2, 11 and 15.

146 Building insulation in thermal and acoustic terms was represented through I_{12} and I_{13} ,
147 which served to value the role played by different roofs when alleviating adverse external
148 weather and noise conditions. Consequently, both indicators are associated with SDGs 7
149 and 11 in what concerns the safeguarding of the energy efficiency and adequate services
150 of buildings.

151 Life cycle cost (I_{14}) was an indicator devoted to measure the economic expenses
152 stemming from the construction, maintenance and eventual demolition of different types
153 of roofs, according to their expected lifetime. As such, this indicator is aligned with the
154 principles of sustainable economic growth highlighted in SDG 8, which in turn acts as a
155 driver for the development of cities reflected in SDG 11.

156 The social dimension of sustainability was incorporated into the assessment through
157 an indicator concerning the contribution of roofs to improving the aesthetical perception
158 of their surroundings (I_{15}). This aspect was expected to impact positively on the
159 development of urban areas towards inclusive and pleasant places to live in, as expressed
160 in the SDG 11.

161 Finally, the last two indicators accounted for functional characteristics of roofs, either
162 in the form of the dead load transmitted to the structure below (I_{16}) or the protection of
163 the waterproofing membrane (I_{17}), which is the most sensitive layer to pathological
164 processes. These factors can help achieving safe and controlled living and working
165 environments, as specified in SDGs 8 and 11.

166 Some of these indicators depended on the climate conditions affecting roofs, such as
167 precipitation, temperature and solar irradiance. To enable the accurate characterisation of
168 different roofs across these weather-based indicators, a trio of scenarios was defined to

169 provide a comprehensive representation of the most characteristic types of climate in
170 Europe.

171 2.2. Climate scenarios

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173 Climate is a crucial factor in the assessment of the performance of roofs in terms of
 174 sustainable development. This study was undertaken under three different weather
 175 scenarios, which coincided with the three main types of climate in Spain [22]: Oceanic,
 176 Continental and Mediterranean. Each climate scenario was associated with a
 177 representative city, as illustrated in Figure 2, in order to obtain the set of parameters
 178 required to implement the methodology in a particular area.

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181 **Figure 2.** Situation map of the cities used as representatives for the three climate scenarios considered:
 182 Continental (Madrid), Oceanic (Santander) and Mediterranean (Valencia)

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184 The first type of climate can be found in the Mediterranean and South-Atlantic coast
 185 of Spain. The precipitation conditions in these areas range from scarce to moderate, with
 186 hot summers and mild winters. Valencia epitomised the characteristics of the
 187 Mediterranean climate, reaching high figures in terms of average maximum temperature
 188 (23 °C) and hours of solar radiation (2696) per year. The annual mean precipitation in this
 189 city is 475 mm, with an average of 46 rainy days.

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191 The Oceanic climate is typical in the north of Spain, consisting of high levels of
 192 precipitation regularly distributed throughout the year and mild and narrow ranges of
 temperature, especially in coastal areas. The reference city for this type of climate was

193 Santander, which highlights by having average values of annual precipitation and
194 maximum temperature of 1,200 mm and 18.5 °C, respectively. The approximate annual
195 number of rainy days (≥ 1 mm) in Santander is 124, with 1649 hours of solar radiation
196 per year.

197 Finally, the interior regions in Spain belong to a Continental climate, which is
198 characterised by scarce rainfall and temperatures with large thermal amplitudes, including
199 warm summers and cold winters favoured by the insolation of these areas from the
200 influence of the sea. Madrid was selected as a representative for this climate, a city with
201 371 mm of precipitation based on a number of 55 wet days per year. The average
202 maximum temperature in the city is 21.1 °C, whilst the annual number of hours of solar
203 radiation amounts to 2749.

204 The description provided about these climates demonstrated the variety of rainfall and
205 temperature conditions covered by the three cities selected as representatives. The
206 combination of the indicators listed in Table 1 with the proposed climate scenarios
207 provided a solid framework with which to assess the contribution of any type of roof to
208 achieving sustainable development.

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210 **2.3. Description of the roof types selected as alternatives**

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212 The set of alternatives proposed to undertake this evaluation was selected to represent the
213 most widely used types of flat roofs, resulting in the four cross-sections illustrated in
214 Figure 3: self-protected, gravel, floating and green roofs. Some of the layers forming these
215 roofs were the same in all cases, such as thermal insulation and sloped concrete. The first
216 consisted of rigid foam panels of Extruded Polystyrene (XPS), whose thickness depended
217 on the insulations requirements for each climate scenario. These roofs were sloped using
218 a 10 cm layer made of cellular concrete with recycled aggregates, including an adequate
219 termination to support either the vapour barrier or the waterproofing membrane. Although
220 the slope in self-protected roofs is commonly provided by the structure, this layer was
221 installed in all the sections for comparative purposes. In this sense, the four types of roofs
222 laid on the same structural system, formed of a unidirectional deck of reinforced beams
223 and concrete blocks, with a 5 cm compression layer. According to the ultimate limit states
224 under bending and shear and the serviceability limit states under deflection and cracking,
225 the thickness of the deck was 20 cm in all roofs.

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Figure 3. Cross-sections of the four types of roofs selected as alternatives a) Self-protected roof b) Gravel roof c) Floating roof d) Green roof

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The first cross-section in Figure 3a) corresponds to a typical design for industrial uses, where flatness, low weight, simplicity and ease of construction are sought. The top layer of the self-protected roof was a white synthetic waterproofing membrane of plasticised Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC), manufactured through a calendaring process and reinforced with a polyester fibre mesh. This membrane was resistant to weathering and solar radiation, having a weight of 2.5 kg/m^2 [23]. Asphalt waterproofing membranes were not considered because of their higher embodied carbon and energy. A vapour barrier made of transparent Low Density Transparent Polyethylene (LDPE), with a thickness of 0.2 mm and a weight of 0.18 kg/m^2 [24], was included between the thermal insulation and the sloped concrete.

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The type of roof shown in Figure 3b) was non walkable due to its gravel finish, except for repair or maintenance purposes. This gravel protection layer was made of white aggregates with a diameter between 16 and 32 mm, a thickness of 7 cm and a slope between 1 and 3%, in order to prevent material displacements [25]. The density of the aggregates was 20 kN/m^3 , according to the safety objectives of the Spanish Technical Building Code [26]. Below was placed an anti-punching separation layer of non-woven geotextile formed by 100% Polypropylene (PP), with a weight of 250g/m^2 [27]. The waterproofing membrane was similar to that defined for the self-protected roof, although there was no colour requirement in this case due to the position of the layer [28].

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The floating roof represented in Figure 3c) consisted of a set of slabs placed on a series of plots, leaving open joints and enabling water filtering [25]. This system creates a ventilated air chamber between the protection and insulation layers. The slabs were made of white concrete with recycled aggregates, with a thickness of 4 cm and a density of 25

254 kN/m³ [26,29]. The plots were adjustable supports of 100% recyclable propylene
255 copolymer, with a range of heights between 122 and 197 mm and a base with a diameter
256 of 186 mm [30]. The suitable distribution of the loads transmitted by the plots to the
257 thermal insulation was guaranteed by a 1.5 cm layer of mortar with a density of 20 kN/m³
258 [26] and a fiberglass mesh to provide flexural and cracking resistance. Besides, a LDPE
259 separation layer with a thickness of 0.2 mm and a weight of 0.18 kg/m² [2] was included
260 below the mortar to prevent its potential incompatibility with the thermal insulation.

261 The type of green roof depicted in Figure 3d) was extensive, which corresponds to
262 substrate thicknesses below 15 or at most 20 cm and small-sized vegetation [31]. The
263 vegetation in this roof consisted of sedum plants with a weight of 0.12 kN/m² [32], which
264 ensured their applicability in the three climate scenarios considered due to their ease of
265 growth and resistance to water scarcity, solar radiation and high temperatures [25]. The
266 substrate was formed of recycled aggregates, compost and inert soil in different
267 proportions [33–35]. This layer had a saturated unit weight of 20 kN/m³ [26] and a
268 thickness of 10 cm, a value that enabled the plants taking root successfully. A separation
269 and filtration layer consisting of a polypropylene-based geotextile with a weight of 300
270 g/m² [36] was placed between the substrate and the drainage layer, made of High-Density
271 Polyethylene (HDPE) with a thickness of 60 mm and a weight of 1.75 kg/m² [37]. In
272 addition, a 0.5 mm thick weatherproof polyethylene sheet with a weight of 0.475 kg/m²
273 [38] was included below to prevent the perforation of underlying layers by the roots.

274 The description of these four alternatives, coupled with the definition of the indicators
275 shown in Table 1 and the climate scenarios represented in Figure 2, provided a complete
276 characterisation of the Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) problem concerning the
277 sustainability-based assessment of different roof types, which was addressed as presented
278 in next subsections.

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280 **2.4. Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA)**

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282 The determination of the contribution of roofs to sustainable development under different
283 climate conditions was approached with the support of MCDA, which enabled their
284 evaluation across the indicators proposed. The MCDA framework designed for this
285 purpose was based on the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and the Technique for Order
286 of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS), which were implemented after
287 refining the initial set of indicators according to the feedback received from a group of
288 building-related experts.

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290 **2.4.1. Refinement of the initial list of indicators**

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292 To ensure the soundness and validity of this investigation, a questionnaire based on the
293 original list of indicators in Table 1 was prepared to enable its subsequent refinement and

294 weighting. This questionnaire was addressed to a panel of experts formed of professionals
295 related to the building industry, such as experts in structures, energetic efficiency, green
296 roofs and/or planning and management of urban areas. Their origin included the academy
297 and construction sectors, as well as different manufacturers of materials.

298 The questionnaires sent to the experts were prepared in spreadsheets, in order to use
299 a familiar format for all the addressees. The first sheet included general information about
300 the aim of this study and the instructions required to fill the questionnaire in correctly. A
301 brief definition of each indicator was provided in the next sheet, anticipating the last step
302 in which the experts had to express their opinions about the importance of the elements
303 in Table 1 according to four-level dropdown lists: very important (VI), important (I),
304 slightly important (SI) and unimportant (UI). The last sheet also left room for judging the
305 original list of indicators in terms of completeness, such that the experts could suggest
306 the removal and/or addition of some of them, as well as their weight in the case of new
307 factors.

308 The responses collected from the panel of experts enabled producing a refined list of
309 indicators, taking into account their opinions about how to evaluate the contribution of
310 roofs to sustainable development comprehensively. Furthermore, their valuations
311 regarding the importance of the indicators enabled determining their weights in the next
312 step of the methodology.

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314 **2.4.2. Weighting of the refined list of indicators**

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316 The weighting of the refined set of indicators was undertaken through the AHP method
317 [39], which seeks to determine the relative importance between two elements according
318 to a pairwise comparison scale. A simplified version of this scale was used to quantify
319 the weights of the indicators (Table 2), consistent with the reduced number of levels of
320 importance considered in the questionnaires, which were four (VI, I, SI and UI) to
321 facilitate their fulfilment by the experts.

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Table 2. Adapted scale to compare the relative importance between indicators

Importance (I_{j_1} vs I_{j_2})	Value	Possible cases
I_{j_1} is three levels of importance above I_{j_2}	7	VI vs UI
I_{j_1} is two levels of importance above I_{j_2}	5	VI vs SI I vs UI
I_{j_1} is one level of importance above I_{j_2}	3	VI vs I I vs LI LI vs UI
I_{j_1} is at the same level of importance that I_{j_2}	1	VI vs VI I vs I SI vs SI UI vs UI
I_{j_1} is one level of importance below I_{j_2}	1/3	UI vs LI LI vs I I vs VI
I_{j_1} is two levels of importance below I_{j_2}	1/5	UI vs I SI vs VI
I_{j_1} is three levels of importance below I_{j_2}	1/7	UI vs VI

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The comparisons made across the refined list of indicators using Table 1 yielded a reciprocal comparison matrix $[M]$, whose validity was evaluated according to the Consistency Ratio ($C.R.$) as formulated in Eq. (1). This term depends on the maximum eigenvalue (λ_{max}) and the size (s) of $[M]$, as well as on the average consistency index of a set of comparison matrices generated randomly ($R.I.$).

$$C.R. = \frac{\lambda_{max} - s}{R.I.} < 0.1 \quad (1)$$

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Since the calculation of the importance of the indicators stemmed from the comparisons made by a group of experts, an additional mechanism was needed to synthesize them all into a single vector of weights. This was carried out through the distance-based aggregation method proposed in Jato-Espino (2018) [40], which starts by allocating weights to all the m experts according to the Euclidean distance between their pairwise comparisons $x_{I_{j_1}I_{j_2}}$, in order to give more importance to those proving to be more similar to the remaining respondents. Hence, the weight w_{e_k} of an expert was determined from their distance $d_{e_{k_1}e_{k_2}}$ to the remaining experts p , as expressed in Eq. **Error!**

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$$w_{e_k} = \frac{1 / \sum_{k=1}^p d_{e_{k_1}e_{k_2}}}{\sum_{k=1}^p \left(1 / \sum_{k=1}^p d_{e_{k_1}e_{k_2}} \right)} \Leftrightarrow d_{e_{k_1}e_{k_2}} = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n \left(\ln x_{I_{j_1}I_{j_2}e_{k_1}} - \ln x_{I_{j_1}I_{j_2}e_{k_2}} \right)^2} \quad (2)$$

342

343 The opinions provided by the experts were aggregated into a matrix formed of
 344 consensual comparisons $x_{I_{j_1}I_{j_2}^c}$ through the geometric mean of the individual responses
 345 collected (Eq. (3)). In turn, these values were used to determine the weights w_{I_j} of the n
 346 indicators included in the refined list through the application of Eq. (3).

$$w_{I_j} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n x_{I_{j_1}I_{j_2}^c}}}}{\sum \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{1}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n x_{I_{j_1}I_{j_2}^c}}}} \Leftrightarrow x_{I_{j_1}I_{j_2}^c} = \left(\prod_{k=1}^p \ln x_{I_{j_1}I_{j_2}^c}^{w_{e_k}} \right)^{1/\sum_{k=1}^p w_{e_k}} \quad (3)$$

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349 2.4.3. Assessment of the alternatives across the refined list of indicators

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351 The evaluation of the contribution of the alternatives depicted in Figure 3 to sustainability
 352 according to their performance across the refined and weighted indicators was
 353 accomplished using the TOPSIS method [41]. This technique consists of determining the
 354 closeness of the roof types (A_i) to the positive and negative ideal solutions to this MCDA
 355 problem. To this end, TOPSIS was applied according to the following steps:

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- 357 1. Determine the ratings r_{ij} of each alternative A_i across the indicators I_j .
- 358
- 359 2. Calculate the normalised ratings n_{ij} according to Eq. (4), which prevents the rank
 360 reversal of alternatives by yielding the most suitable alternative to the problem in
 361 absolute terms ($\max_i z_j$ and $\min_i z_j$) [42].

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$$n_{ij} = \begin{cases} \frac{r_{ij}}{\max_i z_j}, & \text{if } I_j \text{ is a benefit indicator} \\ \frac{\min_i z_j}{r_{ij}}, & \text{if } I_j \text{ is a cost indicator} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

363

- 364 3. Multiply the normalised ratings n_{ij} by the weights w_{I_j} to produce the weighted
 365 normalised ratings v_{ij} .

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- 367 4. Compute the positive (A^+) and negative (A^-) ideal solutions as formulated in Eq.
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$$A^+ = w_j$$

$$A^- = w_j \cdot \frac{n_{ij} \left(\min_i z_j \right)}{n_{ij} \left(\max_i z_j \right)} \quad (5)$$

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5. Obtain the Euclidean distance (d_i^+ and d_i^-) from each alternative A_i to A^+ and A^- , according to Eq. (6).

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$$d_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^+)^2} \quad (6)$$

$$d_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^-)^2}$$

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6. Compare the Relative Closeness (RC_i) between each alternative A_i and the ideal solution through Eq. (7), such that $0 \leq RC_i \leq 1$. Hence, the higher the RC_i of an alternative, the more that alternative contributed to sustainable development.

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$$RC_i = \frac{d_i^-}{d_i^+ + d_i^-} \quad (7)$$

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380 **3. Results and discussion**

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390 **3.1. Refinement of the initial list of indicators**

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The number of responses collected from all the experts addressed was 23, a figure large enough to enable drawing solid inferences henceforth. Table 3 summarises their opinions in what concerns the importance allocated to the list of indicators shown in Table 1,

395 according to the levels of importance defined: very important (VI), important (I), slightly
396 important (SI) and unimportant (UI).

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Table 3. Levels of importance allocated by the experts to the initial indicators

I_j	Indicator	Level of importance			
		VI	I	SI	UI
I_1	Albedo coefficient	7	9	7	0
I_2	Solar power	12	9	2	0
I_3	Carbon sequestration	6	8	8	1
I_4	Embedded carbon	2	12	9	0
I_5	Embedded energy	6	9	8	0
I_6	Runoff attenuation	7	6	8	2
I_7	Water purification	2	7	13	1
I_8	Reduction of runoff temperature	0	3	14	6
I_9	Biodiversity	2	9	12	0
I_{10}	Agricultural productivity	1	4	9	9
I_{11}	Recycled materials	2	11	9	1
I_{12}	Thermal insulation	20	2	0	1
I_{13}	Noise control	8	5	9	1
I_{14}	Life cycle cost	11	11	1	0
I_{15}	Aesthetics	7	9	5	2
I_{16}	Dead load	4	9	9	1
I_{17}	Roof protection	5	11	7	0

399

400 One of the first actions undertaken to refine the list of indicators consisted of removing
401 I_8 , due to the low importance allocated by the addressees to the reduction of runoff
402 temperature provided by the roofs. Another decision made was merging agricultural
403 productivity (I_{10}) with biodiversity (I_9) into a new indicator (I_9), since the former was the
404 second aspect receiving the lowest scores.

405 Four experts coincided in the need for including a new indicator related to the social
406 use of roofs as spaces for recreation. In this case, the solution adopted affected the existing
407 indicator of aesthetics (I_{15}), which evolved to incorporate these aspects into a new
408 indicator (I_{14}) that continued taking into account the impact of roofs on the perception of
409 inhabitants.

410 Another indicator that was initially disregarded and suggested by several experts
411 concerned the capacity of some roofs for controlling relative humidity through the water
412 lost via evapotranspiration processes. These comments led to the addition of a new
413 indicator (I_8) devoted to account for this factor under the climate scenarios considered,
414 resulting in a refined list of 16 indicators.

415

416 3.2. Weighting of the refined list of indicators

417

418 The levels of importance allocated to the indicators remaining in the list after the
 419 refinement process were those provided by the experts in Table 3. Biodiversity and
 420 agricultural productivity was scored with the highest level of importance corresponding
 421 to one of the two aspects into which this new indicator was originally divided (I_9 and I_{10}
 422 in Table 3). Similarly, the social use of roofs was scored with the highest mark between
 423 the values assigned to the initial indicator of aesthetics and those associated with the role
 424 of roofs as spaces for recreation. Finally, the control of relative humidity provided by
 425 roofs was rated as unimportant (UI), since this was a totally new indicator with no
 426 relationship to any of the aspects initially considered in Table 1.

427 Once the level of importance allocated by each expert to the indicators contained in
 428 the refined list was established, 23 pairwise comparison matrices were built according to
 429 Table 2. The highest value of $C.R.$ obtained in these matrices through Eq. (1) was 0.083,
 430 which ensured the consistency of all the comparisons made by the experts ($C.R. < 0.1$).
 431 Then, the importance of the opinions of the experts was computed based on their
 432 similarity of thought, as expressed in Eq. (2). In turn, this enabled determining the values
 433 reflecting the consensual point of view of the whole panel of experts, such that the
 434 resulting comparison matrix was almost perfectly consistent ($C.R. = 0.002$). To end this
 435 step, Eq. (3) was applied to calculate the weights of the indicators (Table 4).

436

437 **Table 4.** Weights (w_j) of the indicators included in the refined list after the feedback provided by the
 438 experts

I_j	Indicator	Units	w_j
I_1	Albedo coefficient	Dimensionless	0.066
I_2	Solar power	%	0.100
I_3	Carbon sequestration	g C/m ²	0.058
I_4	Embedded carbon	kg CO ₂ eq./m ²	0.050
I_5	Embedded energy	MJ/m ²	0.060
I_6	Runoff attenuation	%	0.053
I_7	Water purification	Score	0.040
I_8	Relative humidity control	mm/day	0.014
I_9	Biodiversity and agricultural productivity	Yes/No	0.045
I_{10}	Recycled materials	%	0.048
I_{11}	Thermal insulation	cm	0.137
I_{12}	Noise control	t/m ³	0.062
I_{13}	Life cycle cost	€/m ²	0.097
I_{14}	Social use	Score	0.056
I_{15}	Dead load	kN/m ²	0.052
I_{16}	Roof protection	±°C	0.062

439

440 On the one hand, the indicators achieving the highest weights were thermal insulation
 441 (I_{11}), solar power (I_2) and life cycle cost (I_{13}). These results highlighted the experts'
 442 awareness of the need for harmonising the three pillars of sustainable development, since

443 these indicators were representatives for the social, environmental and economic
444 dimensions of sustainability, respectively.

445 Although the relevance of I_{11} and I_{13} as drivers for social comfort and economic
446 development was completely justified, the importance allocated to I_2 might be slightly
447 controversial nowadays, since improvements in the production of photovoltaic energy are
448 currently feasible only at more than 25°C [43]. However, the weight reached by this
449 indicator was in line with the upward trend in the use of renewable energy, which suggests
450 that the photovoltaic potential of roofs should be increasingly taken into account in the
451 assessment of their contribution to sustainability.

452 On the other hand, both the water-related indicators (I_6 , I_7 and I_8) and biodiversity
453 and agricultural productivity (I_9) were among the aspects obtaining the lowest weights.
454 These were exclusive characteristics of the green roof, such that their reduced importance
455 contributed to increasing the robustness of the results to achieve in subsequent steps,
456 preventing bias towards this alternative.

457

458 **3.3. Assessment of the alternatives across the refined list of indicators**

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460 The assessment of the sustainability of the roofs represented in Figure 3 started with the
461 quantification of their performance across the refined list of indicators. This task may be
462 influenced by the climate scenarios described in Figure 2, since some indicators referred
463 to intrinsic properties of roofs. Moreover, the quantification of some indicators stemmed
464 from applying analytical and structural calculations, whilst some others were
465 characterised according to values found in specialised literature. Table 5 compiles the
466 ratings of each of the four alternatives considered with respect to the indicators in Table
467 4.

468 The Albedo coefficient (I_1) only depends on the materials forming the roof. In general,
469 common values of Albedo in urban surfaces (pavements and roofs) range from 0.1 to 0.25
470 [1,44]. Since this study considered white and reflective materials to boost sustainability,
471 the Albedo coefficients for the self-protected, gravel, floating and green roofs were set at
472 0.5 [45], 0.6 [46,47], 0.3 [48] and 0.275 [49], respectively.

473 The rating of the self-protected, gravel and floating roofs in terms of solar power (I_2)
474 was 0%, since the effect of these alternatives on photovoltaic cells are negligible. Instead,
475 the performance of photovoltaic cells installed on green roofs might vary from 0.08 to
476 8.3% [50] depending on the weather. Values of 3, 2 and 4% were allocated to the
477 Mediterranean, Oceanic and Continental climates. Carbon sequestration (I_3) was also
478 exclusive of green roofs. According to the Sedum extensive green roof defined in Figure
479 3, a value of 375 g/m² [51] was adopted to rate the potential of this alternative for this
480 purpose.

481 The calculation of the embedded carbon (I_4) and energy (I_5) was undertaken with the
482 support of the Inventory of Carbon & Energy (ICE) [52], which contains these data for a

483 multitude of construction materials. There were variations depending on the climate
484 scenario, mainly due to the differences in the thermal insulation. The aggregated
485 multiplication of the mass of the layers forming the roofs by their embedded carbon and
486 energy yielded the values shown in Table 5. In those cases in which specific materials
487 were missing in the ICE, the most similar alternatives available were chosen as
488 substitutes.

489 The only alternative contributing to reducing runoff (I_6) was the green roof; however,
490 its capacity in this sense depends on a variety of factors, including pre-existing humidity
491 and rainfall intensity and duration [53–56]. From higher to lower, the climate scenarios
492 achieved the following values in relation to these aspects (pre-existing humidity, rainfall
493 intensity, rainfall duration) [57,58]: Mediterranean (medium, 160 mm/h, low), Oceanic
494 (high, 125 mm/h, high) and Continental (low, 125 mm/h, medium). The correspondence
495 of these features with the characteristics of different green roofs in several cities around
496 the globe studied by Gregoire and Clausen (2011) [59] led to define a runoff retention
497 potential of 60, 35 and 45% for Valencia, Santander and Madrid, respectively.

498 The rating of water purification (I_7) was derived from two studies conducted by
499 Mendez et al. (2011) [60] and Farreny et al. (2011) [61]. Although the cross-sections
500 represented in Figure 3 were addressed in either one of the two investigations, they both
501 coincided in testing a metallic roof that was taken as a reference. Therefore, those water
502 quality parameters achieving similar values for the metallic roof in both studies (total
503 suspended solids, nitrate and total organic carbon) were used to determine a normalised
504 index for the roof types in Figure 3, such that the higher this value, the higher water
505 quality.

506 Relative humidity control (I_8) was another indicator that only affected the green roof
507 schematised in Figure 3d), since it depended on the evapotranspiration produced by
508 vegetation. Based on several studies consisting of onsite measurements of
509 evapotranspiration in green roofs [62–65], values of 3, 3.5 and 2.5 mm/day were assigned
510 to this indicator under the Mediterranean, Oceanic and Continental scenarios. Similarly,
511 the green roof was the only alternative capable of providing a suitable space for
512 biodiversity and agricultural growth (I_9), resulting in a binary indicator as shown in Table
513 5.

514 The percentage of recycled materials (I_{10}) was calculated by comparison with the total
515 volume of the roof types in Figure 3, according to information provided by different
516 manufacturers. Hence, the gravel layer in Figure 3b) was assumed to come from a quarry,
517 in order to ensure a high Albedo coefficient. Similarly, the sand and cement in the mortar
518 bed shown in Figure 3c) was considered not recyclable. Instead, all the plastic materials
519 forming the plots in Figure 3c) [30] and the waterproofing [66] and thermal insulation
520 [67,68] layers were 100% recyclable, as well as the substrate in Figure 3d), which
521 stemmed from a combination of recycled materials, compost and inert soil [33–35]. The

522 percentage of recycled aggregates in the sloped concrete and the floating slabs in Figure
523 3c) was set at 65 [69] and 50% [26,29], respectively.

524 The thickness of the thermal insulation layer (I_{11}) was calculated as specified in the
525 Spanish Technical Building Code [70], whereby the building envelope must meet certain
526 requirements in terms of thermal transmittance according to its surrounding climate, such
527 that the limits for Valencia, Santander and Madrid were set at 0.45, 0.41 and 0.38 m² k/w,
528 respectively. The comparison between these values of thermal transmittance and the
529 aggregate of the thermal conductivity of the layers [71] yielded the thickness of the
530 thermal insulation layer in the three climate scenarios considered.

531 The acoustic insulation responsible for noise control (I_{12}) was determined from the
532 density of 1 m² of the cross-sections represented in Figure 3 [72]. In turn, this density was
533 computed from the thickness and specific weight of the layers, which were established
534 from data acquired both from manufacturers and the catalogue of constructive elements
535 found in the Spanish standards [71].

536 In contrast with previous studies where the calculation of the life cycle cost of roofs
537 (I_{13}) included their energetic, hydrologic and environmental benefits, this indicator was
538 only evaluated based on construction, maintenance and demolition costs, since other
539 indirect aspects were addressed through specific indicators (Table 4). Hence, I_{13} was
540 calculated as annual €/m² according to two construction cost databases [73,74] and
541 considering that the lifetime for the self-protected, gravel, floating and green roofs was
542 15, 25, 30 and 50 years, respectively [75].

543 The indicator about the social use (I_{11}) of the roofs was scored according to reasonable
544 assumptions in what concerns their role as spaces for recreation and aesthetic enhancers.
545 Consequently, the self-protected, gravel, floating and green roofs were rated with scores
546 of 0, 0.25, 0.65 and 1, based on their walkability and contribution to improving the quality
547 perception of the urban landscape.

548 Similarly to the process adopted for characterising I_{12} , the dead load (I_{15}) of the roofs
549 was determined as the aggregate of the specific weights and thicknesses of their layers.
550 Finally, the protection of the waterproofing membrane (I_{16}) was rated according to the
551 thermal amplitude of this layer, which was 0, 5 or 55°C depending on the type of roof
552 [25] (Table 5).

553

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Table 5. Ratings of the roof types across the refined indicators

I_j	$\min_i z_j$	$\max_i z_j$	Scenario	Roof type			
				Self-protected	Gravel	Floating	Green
I_1	0.100	0.500	All	0.500	0.400	0.300	0.275
I_2	0.000	4.000	*	0	0	0	3
			**	0	0	0	2
			***	0	0	0	4
I_3	0	375	All	0	0	0	375
I_4	35.00	60.00	*	33.59	33.65	51.35	38.81
			**	33.59	34.71	52.41	39.86
			***	34.64	35.76	53.46	39.86
I_5	425.00	725.00	*	365.56	370.28	488.34	412.90
			**	365.56	398.63	516.69	441.25
			***	393.91	426.99	545.04	441.25
I_6	0	60	*	0	0	0	60
			**	0	0	0	35
			***	0	0	0	45
I_7	0	1	All	0.428	0.681	0.528	0.294
I_8	0.0	3.5	*	0	0	0	3.0
			**	0	0	0	3.5
			***	0	0	0	2.5
I_9	0	1	All	0	0	0	1
I_{10}	50.00	100.00	*	79.65	55.27	67.81	87.32
			**	79.65	57.10	69.22	87.76
			***	80.77	58.78	70.52	87.76
I_{11}	7.50	15.00	*	6.28	5.93	5.66	5.34
			**	7.04	6.69	6.42	6.10
			***	7.71	7.36	7.09	6.77
I_{12}	0.800	1.350	*	1.191	1.375	1.325	1.473
			**	1.191	1.311	1.256	1.423
			***	1.128	1.253	1.194	1.423
I_{13}	9.000	12.500	*	8.560	5.359	6.147	5.697
			**	8.160	6.048	5.844	5.307
			***	8.353	6.192	5.941	5.487
I_{14}	0.00	1.00	All	0.00	0.25	0.65	1.00
I_{15}	2.000	4.250	*	2.049	3.447	3.351	4.190
			**	2.049	3.450	3.353	4.193
			***	2.052	3.453	3.357	4.193
I_{16}	0	55	All	55	5	0	0

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The sequential application of the steps of the TOPSIS method as specified in Eqs. (4), (5), (6) and (7) enabled normalising and weighting the ratings included in Table 5, as well as computing the Relative Closeness (RC_i) between the alternatives under evaluation and the ideal solution to this MCDA problem. Figure 4 shows the values of RC_i achieved by each alternative under the different climate scenarios considered.

Figure 4. Relative Closeness (RC_i) between the roof types and an ideally sustainable solution

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The results illustrated in Figure 4 demonstrated that the green roof was by far the most sustainable solution under all climate scenarios, despite being the cross-section providing the worst scores in terms of Albedo coefficient (I_1), water purification (I_7) and dead load (I_{15}). The second best alternative was the floating roof, whilst the self-protected and gravel roofs achieved the lowest values of RC_i in all cases.

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One of the main reasons behind these rankings related to the exclusive benefits of the green roof, since only this alternative contributed to 5 of the 16 indicators in Table 4: solar power (I_2), carbon sequestration (I_3), runoff attenuation (I_6), relative humidity control (I_8) and biodiversity and agricultural productivity (I_9). Another aspect justifying the preponderance of the green roof was its extended lifetime, which allows a gradual amortisation of its high initial investment, yielding the lowest values in terms of lifecycle cost (I_{13}). Finally, this alternative also highlighted by its thermal and acoustic benefits in comparison with the other roof types, as well as by its potential for including recycled materials.

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The differences between the self-protected and gravel roofs were almost negligible, to the extent that they outperformed each other by very narrow margins depending on the climate scenario. The Mediterranean climate was found to favour the gravel solution, and vice versa for the Oceanic and Continental conditions. This was associated with the thickness of the thermal insulation layer, which was higher for the Mediterranean climate in the case of the self-protected roof. Instead, both types of roofs had the same values for the two other climate scenarios (Figure 3), such that the positive ratings of the self-protected solution in terms of Albedo coefficient (I_1) or recycled materials (I_{10}) justified its dominance under these circumstances.

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Although the green roof achieved the first position in all scenarios, the scores reached by the alternatives varied depending on the climate conditions. Hence, the four roof types achieved their maximum degree of sustainability under the Mediterranean climate,

591 probably due to its lower thermal insulation requirements in comparison with the other
592 scenarios, which resulted in more favourable values across several indicators. The
593 minimum contribution to sustainability of the green roof stemmed from the Oceanic
594 scenario, since its exclusive indicators were less beneficial in Santander. Instead, the
595 remaining alternatives reached their lowest values of RC_i under the Continental climate,
596 since this was the most demanding scenario in terms of thermal insulation.

597 Overall, the results compiled in Figure 4 indicated that there is still room for
598 improvement in the design of sustainable roofs, since the values of RC_i achieved by the
599 green roof were far from a completely ideal solution ($RC_i = 1$). This distance was mainly
600 caused by three indicators across which this alternative was poorly scored: Albedo
601 coefficient (I_1), water purification (I_7) and dead load (I_{15}). Potential solutions to palliate
602 these drawbacks might consist of the use of whiter aggregates, geotextiles or lighter
603 materials in the corresponding layers forming the green roof.

604

605 **4. Conclusions**

606

607 The results obtained in this research demonstrated the suitability of the proposed approach
608 to assess the contribution of different roof types to achieving the Sustainable
609 Development Goals (SDGs) established by the United Nations. This was accomplished
610 through the application of a Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) methodology,
611 which was found to provide a solid and comprehensive means to determine the degree of
612 sustainability of roofs under different climate scenarios, based on their valuation across a
613 series of energetic, hydrologic, environmental, economic, social and structural indicators.

614 The opinions provided by a panel of international experts in the building industry
615 enabled refining and improving the list of sustainability indicators, ensuring that all
616 relevant aspects from the academic, professional and institutional points of view were
617 taken into account. The participation of the experts also guaranteed that the weights
618 obtained were representative for the concerns of the building sector in terms of
619 sustainability. In fact, the three most important indicators according to the comparisons
620 made by the experts highlighted the need for integrating the three pillars of sustainable
621 development, since they addressed economic (life cycle cost), environmental (solar
622 power) and social (thermal insulation) issues.

623 Green roofs emerged as the most sustainable solution under all climate scenarios, due
624 to their specific energy, water and ecosystem-related services and the cost, recycling and
625 comfort benefits they provide in comparison with conventional alternatives. Still, the
626 design of green roofs should be improved to better address the targets included in the
627 SDGs by including reflective, filter and lightweight materials. As a part of green
628 infrastructure, this type of roofs can also help in the fight against Climate Change, which
629 has consolidated as one the humanity's greatest challenges in the future, especially in
630 urban areas.

631 In consequence, green roofs can be included in the design of urban planning strategies
 632 oriented to the progressive replacement of built-up surfaces by green infrastructure. Their
 633 advantages in comparison with conventional roofs should be disseminated and stimulated
 634 by public entities and authorities, in order to promote the implementation of these
 635 solutions in both newly constructed and existing roofs. In terms of research, further efforts
 636 should be devoted to consider the addition of new indicators and climate scenarios,
 637 conduct sensitivity analyses on the weights and ratings assigned to the indicators and
 638 explore complementary lines of investigation, such as sustainable agriculture and food
 639 security, structural optimisation based on the influence of the dead load on old buildings
 640 or resilience assessment of the different layers forming green roofs.

641

642 **Acknowledgments**

643

644 This paper was possible thanks to the research project SUPRIS-SUREs (Ref. BIA2015-
 645 65240-C2-1-R MINECO/FEDER, UE), financed by the Spanish Ministry of Economy
 646 and Competitiveness with funds from the State General Budget (PGE) and the European
 647 Regional Development Fund (ERDF).

648

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